

A Study on Impact of Digitalization in Education

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Abstract

Technology can become the ‘wings’ that will allow the education system to fly farther and faster than ever before; if we will allow it.”

With increasing awareness and technical progress of society, it is required to cultivate learning skills that could help in pace with the development of science and technology. Education in the twenty-first century is the center from which all changes and improvements arise. Today knowledge and information are the core keys to obtaining productivity, competition, wealth, and comfort. Education systems have focused on various approaches for increasing and gaining better-quality education. In order to develop the human capital, it is essential to look at our school teachings and see if our education is succeeding in step with the world that is changing and developing quickly. In India from last few years, there has been a significant rise in Virtual Classrooms at different levels of learning with evolution of know-hows such as cloud, virtual data centers and virtualization. There is a vast prospect for technology to be integrated with the education system. The purpose of this paper is to give an overview of digital education, the future scope, and possible challenges of the society for moving towards digital education.

Keywords: Digital Education, Scope of Digitalization, Challenges.

Objectives of the Study

1. To know the influence of technology in education.
2. To understand the attitudes of the students towards electronic teaching.
3. To study the attitudes of the teachers towards the use of technology.

Introduction

In this 21st century technology, has no bounds. Tremendous changes in the style of the human being, which are attributed to the contribution of technology and has experienced in all most all the sphere of human life, including education in various ways and directions. After the invention of paper and the printing press, it became possible to record information as a result of which learners were able to refer to documents needed for learning. The paper revolution has given way for the invention of electronic machines, especially

audio, video, and computers; smart phones, laptops, and tablet are no more unknown words. These inventions have made a significant change in the delivery of learning materials inside a classroom. For example, modern school classrooms often make use of televisions, video, cassette players, and computers. It is being used as tools of instruction and learning in science and other subjects. These tools have been considered as forms of educational technology. Because of the rapid development of information technology; there is a shift taking place from print-based learning to electronic learning through the use of advanced computing and telecommunication technologies. In the developed nations and even in developing countries, the rapid growth of technology infrastructure has led to the increased availability and use of technology.

In this stage, the education system is upgrading the changing for a better improvement, as this generation's students are not born to be confined by the limits of simple learning as their curiosity is vast and cannot be catered with the system that was designed earlier. The Concept of Digitalization means to transfer face-to-face information delivered by a trainer to digital platforms which aims to increase the standards and efficiency in learning which is enhanced with features of the current parameters like Audio/video, Text & visual, Animation, Simulation, Applications and activity-based learning.

In most of the developing countries, it is found that the usage of technology in administration is improving the quality of its educational system. Digital instructions are more engaging to today's students over the time. There is a reduction in students appealing for books today because they are very familiar with getting their information from tech-based sources. Many students and teachers are utilizing information and communication technology tools in the form of digital content, presentations, teleconferencing, internet, e-content, eLearning, mobile learning, an electronic classroom, podcasts, and virtual campus to varying degrees.

Significance and Scope

- Education technology is as broad as education itself, which implies the use of various resources like skills, materials, and techniques in an intergraded manner for optimized learning.
- Technology enhances the relationship between instructor and learner by making learning more meaningful and exciting.
- Education technology is not only limited to teaching aids but pervades all over. (At home, in software developments, specification of the problems).
- The report of the Indian National Knowledge Commission affirms a commitment to shape a quality in the educational system to meet the challenges of the 21st century and to increase the competitive advantage in fields of knowledge
- The employment of technological tools in areas like academics, administration, and research has helped in simplifying the work.
- Digitalized Education program enables the learner to acquire problem-solving, decision-making skills and to discover the association of science with health, agriculture, industry, and another aspect of daily life.
- Education technology is seen both as a means as well as service to effect and facilitates better and more productive learning systems.

Challenges

Yet, it has a long way to tread before realizing the actual potential of Digital Education in India. Some of the projecting hurdles are Digital Literacy & Infrastructure, where most of the education systems still do not have the required internet bandwidth, and many are illiterate in digital terminologies and devices. The key challenges that are hampering the integration of digitalization in the classrooms are as follows:

- Educators are contented to use the traditional method of teaching henceforth resist to change, and to come out of their comfort zones. Technological experimentations are often seen as outside the scope of their job descriptions.
- Most of the schools are not still equipped with the type of technological devices they should use in order to understand their requirements and work accordingly. The availability of gadgets is essential for proper and smooth functioning without any hindrances.
- Institutions need to prepare themselves to make students and teachers to work together on a device with timely guidance for effective use of technology.
- Kids today are more active a pro when it comes to technical things which effect their learning.
- Teachers should interact and engage with the students to learn, along with them to enjoy the benefits of technology.
- Fewer Educators have this Fear of beginners with new know-hows and scared to experiment with new skills with the thought of having to learn it once for all from the idea of integrating technology.
- Educators aren't provided with adequate training and technical support, with so many roles to play. There a shortage of time to practice with new and changing technologies.
- Technology can enhance the performance of educators, professors, the entire school and university systems. The skills of the students and educators of the 21st- century will include basic literacy, scientific, economic, and digital literacy in addition to various subject areas.
- Most of the developing nations are facing grave problems like poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, environment degradation, regional disparities, etc. Under these circumstances, technology can provide solutions to these issues.

Conclusion

Technology is an integral part of living in the 20th century, referred to as the fourth revolution, accompanied by challenges and opportunities. The aim of the article is to explain the difficulty of technology as embedded in other common developments which can include and exclude. Technology is understood as more than gadgets that can be utilized, but also implies an attitude towards life.

The view, to mobilize, optimize the available human, technological, knowledgeable resources because human mind has the capacity to store only a certain amount of information, and this limitation can be very unsatisfying to those who frequently seek new information to meet their level of curiosity. Inevitably, teachers need to adjust their teaching techniques to follow those that involve the transfer of pedagogy from the traditional means to electronic-assisted classrooms, so that they can satisfy present-day students who might otherwise face problems of adapting to the new information age. This has directed to develop new techniques of teaching and learning in the era of globalization.

In order to avoid the misuse of these valuable technologies which come with high costs, a lot of experimentation needs to be done. Thus, the scope of the use of technology can be appreciated for both the teachers and students who are the key stakeholders in the process of education and for whom electronic classroom happens to be an innovation for making teaching and learning more effective.

The benefits of technology as a tool for learning, enable the teachers and the learners to perform their jobs more effectively in pursuit of knowledge. According to a 2012 UK study of young people by the National Literacy Trust, the number of children who read books not required in their schooling has dropped a full 25% during the last decade, with only about 25% of children choosing to read of their own accord. Successful integration of new technologies into teaching and learning

processes will inevitably require teachers’ that they change their attitudes and teaching paradigms. Such changes will oblige them to adapt to new methodological approaches.

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